

R O O T L I N K S

Strengthening Roots, Creating Links

ENABLING PRIMARY PRODUCERS TO THRIVE IN THE BIOECONOMY

Primary producers are vital to Europe's future. RootLinks strengthens the role of agriculture, forestry, and blue economy producers in circular bio-based value chains, and creates links to new opportunities.

We help producers grow across five dimensions.

Awareness

Cooperation

Networking

Capacity Building

Business Models

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At the core of RootLinks is the Working Group on Primary Producers (WGPP), established under the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU).

Bringing together representatives from agriculture, forestry, and the blue economy, the WGPP provides a collaborative platform for dialogue and coordinated action.

Through an inclusive governance model and co-creative processes, RootLinks facilitates the development of a shared Action Plan that reflects and advances producers' priorities.

HOW TO BECOME A MEMBER

WHO CAN JOIN?

Primary producers with a legal entity, cooperatives or producer organisations, and associations, networks, or advisory services working with primary producers.

LEARN MORE

